

Potentiometric Studies on the Formation of Quaternary Mixed Ligand Complexes of Some Transition Metal Ions

(Miss) SUJATA KHANNA, (Miss) ALKA PRADHAN and G. K. CHATURVEDI

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra-282 002

Manuscript received 10 April 1983, revised 21 November 1983, accepted 13 February 1984

The formation of mixed ligand complexes of the type MABC, where M(II) = Cu(II), Ni(II) or Zn(II), A = iminodiacetic acid (IMDA), B = malonic acid (maln) and C = ethylenediamine (en) or 1,2-propanediamine (pn) have been investigated by pH metric titrations. Evidence is provided for the simultaneous addition of primary ligand (A) and secondary ligand (B) to the metal ion resulting in the formation of an intermediate ternary species, MAB, to which the tertiary ligand (C) probably gets attached resulting in the formation of a soluble hetero-ligand quaternary species. The overall formation constants and thermodynamic parameters for the resulting hetero-ligand species have been evaluated at 25 ± 1 and $35 \pm 1^\circ$ ($\mu = 0.1$ M KNO_3). The relative order of stabilities in terms of metal ions and diamines has been found as $\text{Zn}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+}$; $\text{pn} > \text{en}$, respectively.

LITERATURE reveals that extensive work has been carried out on the ternary complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} in solution¹⁻⁴ from the view point of their stability determination as well as their biocidal activity in solid state⁵⁻⁶. Siegel⁷ has explained the pharmacological activity of Cu^{2+} complexes with a variety of nitrogen containing ligands as well as chelates of other metals of the first transition series. Few references⁸⁻¹⁰ are available on the formation of quaternary complexes of transition metal ions. It is evident from the literature cited that complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} play very effective role in various living processes, and the activity of a metal complex is related to its stability. In the present communication we have studied the quaternary complexes of Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} with some biologically active ligands and have also evaluated the formation constants and the thermodynamic parameters of the resulting complexes. The results are presented in this paper.

Experimental

The chemicals used were either of B.D.H., A.R. or E. Merck grade. Stock solutions of metal nitrates were prepared and standardised by standard methods. The solutions of IMDA, malonic acid and diaminedihydrochlorides¹¹ were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amounts of the respective materials in double distilled water. The experimental procedures were the same as described earlier¹².

Calculations :

The acid dissociation constants of IMDA ($pK_1 = 2.73$, $pK_2 = 9.32$), maln ($pK_1 = 2.33$, $pK_2 = 5.34$), en- 2H^+ ($pK_1 = 7.08$, $pK_2 = 9.78$) and pn- 2H^+ ($pK_1 = 6.96$, $pK_2 = 9.82$) were determined by the method of Chaberek and Martell¹³.

Formation constants for the simultaneous addition of the primary (IMDA) and the secondary (maln) ligands to the metal ion have been evaluated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa¹⁴. For the addition of the tertiary ligand (en/pn) to the intermediate ternary species M^{2+} -IMDA-maln, the method of Thompson and Loraas¹⁵ has been used to evaluate the formation constants.

Results and Discussion

The titration curves of the systems Cu^{2+} -IMDA-maln-en/pn are given in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively, as representatives ones. The curves for the other systems $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Zn}^{2+}$ -IMDA-maln-en/pn being identical, are not included for the sake of brevity.

Free ligands :

Curve a (Figs. 1 and 2) representing the titration of en/pn- 2HCl gives an inflection at $m \sim 1$ ($m = \text{moles of base added per mole of metal ion or ligand}$) which is due to the titration of only one of the protons of diaminedihydrochloride¹⁶.

Curve b (Figs. 1 and 2) depicts the pH-metric titration of malonic acid and shows an inflection at $m = 2$, which may be ascribed to the titration of the two carboxy protons of the dicarboxylic acid¹⁷.

Curve c (Figs. 1 and 2) representing the titration of IMDA exhibits inflections at $m = 1$ and 2, which may be ascribed to the titration of the two carboxy protons¹⁶ of the acid in steps.

Binary systems :

In the systems M^{2+} -IMDA-maln-en/pn, the inflection at $m = 2$ (curves d, e and f; Figs. 1 and 2) and the lowering in pH indicate the formation of 1 : 1 M^{2+} -IMDA-maln-en/pn^{16,17}, respectively.

An additional inflection at $m \sim 3$ in the cases of M^{2+} -IMDA-en/pn is attributed to the disproportionation¹⁶ of the 1 : 1 species into more stable and soluble 1 : 2 species and metal hydroxide (except in the case of Zn^{2+} -en system. A single inflection at $m \sim 3$ in the Zn^{2+} -en system is ascribed to the disproportionation of the 1 : 1 species before its complete formation. The above reactions may be generalized as :

$M = Cu, Ni, Zn$; $A = \text{IMDA/en/pn}$.

The subsequent inflection at $m=4$, in the case of the 1 : 1 M^{2+} -maln system (curve e), may be due to the decomposition¹⁷ of the binary complex into the

Fig. 1. System 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 Cu(II)-IMDA-maln-en.

- a en 2H⁺
- c IMDA
- e 1 : 1 Cu(II)-maln
- g 1 : 1 : 1 Cu(II)-IMDA-en
- i 1 : 1 : 1 Cu(II)-IMDA-maln
- j 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 Cu(II)-IMDA-maln-en
- T, X, X', X'' Theoretical composite curve
- Appearance of ppt.
- b maln
- d 1 : 1 Cu(II)-IMDA
- f 1 : 1 Cu(II)-en
- h 1 : 1 : 1 Cu(II)-maln-en

Fig. 2. System 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 Cu(II)-IMDA-maln-pn.

- a pn 2H⁺
- c IMDA
- e 1 : 1 Cu(II)-maln
- g 1 : 1 : 1 Cu(II)-IMDA-pn
- i 1 : 1 : 1 Cu(II)-IMDA-maln
- j 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 Cu(II)-IMDA-maln-pn
- T, X, X', X'' Theoretical composite curve
- Appearance of ppt.
- b maln
- d 1 : 1 Cu(II)-IMDA
- f 1 : 1 Cu(II)-pn
- h 1 : 1 : 1 Cu(II)-maln-pn

free dicarboxylate ion and metal hydroxide in the higher pH range.

$M = Cu, Ni, Zn$; $Y = \text{maln}$.

Ternary systems :

Curve g for 1 : 1 : 1 M^{2+} -IMDA-en/pn and h for 1 : 1 : 1 M^{2+} -maln-en/pn (Figs. 1 and 2) exhibit inflections at $m=2$ and $m=4$. In the lower buffer region curves g (1 : 1 : 1 M^{2+} -IMDA-en/pn) and h (1 : 1 : 1 M^{2+} -maln-en/pn) superimpose the respective binary systems (1 : 1 M^{2+} -IMDA/maln ; curves d and e) indicating the initial formation of 1 : 1 M^{2+} -IMDA/maln species. The inflection at $m=2$ may be due to the initial formation of specified

TABLE 1—VALUES OF FORMATION CONSTANTS AT 25 ± 1° AND 35 ± 1° (μ = 0.1 M)

System	log K ^M _{MAB}		log K ^{MAB} _{MABC}		Overall formation constants	
	25	35	25	35	25	35
Cu(II)-IMDA-maln-en	12.79 ± 0.17	12.70 ± 0.15	7.65 ± 0.12	7.53 ± 0.11	20.44	20.23
Ni(II)-IMDA-maln-en	11.59 ± 0.16	11.44 ± 0.11	4.99 ± 0.13	4.90 ± 0.12	16.58	16.34
Zn(II)-IMDA-maln-en	11.76 ± 0.23	11.62 ± 0.14	5.13 ± 0.18	5.00 ± 0.10	16.89	16.62
Cu(II)-IMDA-maln-pn	12.79 ± 0.17	12.70 ± 0.15	7.89 ± 0.12	7.78 ± 0.15	20.68	20.48
Ni(II)-IMDA-maln-pn	11.59 ± 0.16	11.44 ± 0.11	5.45 ± 0.12	5.37 ± 0.12	17.04	16.81
Zn(II)-IMDA-maln-pn	11.76 ± 0.23	11.62 ± 0.14	5.99 ± 0.10	5.25 ± 0.14	17.25	16.87

TABLE 2—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

System	ΔF° k cal mol ⁻¹		ΔH° k cal mol ⁻¹	ΔS° cal mol ⁻¹	
	25	35		25	35
Cu(II)-IMDA-maln-en	-27.85	-27.57	-8.921	+63.85	+60.87
Ni(II)-IMDA-maln-en	-22.59	-22.27	-10.082	+41.97	+39.57
Zn(II)-IMDA-maln-en	-23.02	-22.65	-11.342	+39.18	+36.71
Cu(II)-IMDA-maln-pn	-28.18	-27.91	-8.401	+66.37	+63.34
Ni(II)-IMDA-maln-pn	-23.22	-22.91	-9.662	+45.50	+43.01
Zn(II)-IMDA-maln-pn	-23.37	-22.94	-11.762	+38.95	+36.29

binary species. An additional inflection at m=4 is attributed to the attachment of the diamine molecule during which the neutralization of the two hydrochloride protons occurs forming the 1:1:1 M²⁺-IMDA/maln-en/pn species. The non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve^{1,9} X (drawn by adding the horizontal distances of the 1:1 M²⁺-IMDA/maln curve with those of the curve showing the titration of en/pn 2H⁺) with the experimental curves g and h in the region of mixed-ligand complex formation, absence of any heterogeneous phase and the lowering in pH support the formation of above ternary species and can be represented as :

M = Cu, Ni, Zn ; A = IMDA ; B = en 2H⁺/pn 2H⁺.

Curve i (Figs. 1 and 2) represents the titration of 1:1:1 M²⁺-IMDA-maln system. The lowering in pH in comparison to that observed in 1:1 binary systems and an inflection at m=4 may be correlated to the simultaneous addition of both the ligands to the metal ion forming 1:1:1 M²⁺-IMDA-maln species. The non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve^{1,9} X' X'' (X = curve d + curve b and X'' = curve e + curve c) and non-formation of any solid phase support the formation of the soluble ternary species as specified :

Quaternary systems :

Curve j (Figs. 1 and 2) representing the 1:1:1:1 M²⁺-IMDA-maln-en/pn systems, superimposes the

curve i for 1:1:1 M²⁺-IMDA-maln upto m=4 and exhibits an inflection at m=4 indicating the initial formation of 1:1:1 M²⁺-IMDA-maln species prior to the formation of the quaternary species. The addition of tertiary ligands (en/pn) to the intermediate ternary species is indicated by an inflection at m=6. This inflection at m=6, non-formation of any precipitate during the titration and non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve^{1,9} T (curve i + curve a) corroborate the formation of soluble quaternary 1:1:1:1 M²⁺-IMDA-maln-en/pn species as indicated below :

M = Cu, Ni, Zn ; A = IMDA ; B = maln ; C = en/pn 2H⁺.

A comparison of the data of the formation constants for ternary as well as quaternary complexes given in Table 1 indicates the following order of stabilities in terms of metal ions Zn²⁺ < Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ which is in accordance with the William-Irving order²⁰. The order in terms of diamines is pn > en and is in agreement with the reported data^{1,6}.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. J. P. Tandon, Chemistry Department, Rajasthan University, Jaipur for valuable suggestions, to the Agra College authorities for necessary facilities and to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. K. KAPOOR, VINOD KUMARI, R. C. SHARMA and G. B. CHATURVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 686,

KHANNA, PRADHAN & CHATURVEDI : POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE FORMATION ETC.

2. B. AGARWAL, K. DEWEDI, M. CHANDRA, B. AGARWAL and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 93.
3. P. BONONO, S. MUSUMCU, E. RIZZARELLI and S. SAMARTONA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 1851.
4. VINOD KUMARI and G. K. CHATURVEDI, *Agra Univ. J. Res. Sci.*, 1957, **24**, 163.
5. R. C. SHARMA, S. P. TRIPATHI, S. KHANNA and R. S. SHARMA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1981, **50**, 748.
6. S. KHANNA, A. K. JAIN and G. K. CHATURVEDI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1982 **21A**, 206.
7. H. SIGGEL, "Metal Ion in Biological System", Marcel Dekker, Inc., N. Y., Vol. 14, pp. 78-113.
8. VINOD KUMARI and G. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 319.
9. S. RAMAMOORTHY and P. G. MANNING, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1671.
10. S. KOCH and G. ACKERMANN, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1976, **420**, 85.
11. VINOD KUMARI, Ph.D. Thesis, Agra University, 1975.
12. S. KHANNA, R. KUMAR and G. K. CHATURVEDI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19A**, 766.
13. S. CHABEREK and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5052.
14. S. RAMAMOORTHY and M. SANTAPPA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 581.
15. L. C. THOMPSON and J. A. LORAAS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 89.
16. G. SHARMA and J. P. TANDON, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1970, **25b**, 22.
17. VINOD KUMARI, R. C. SHARMA and G. K. CHATURVEDI, *Bull. de. l' Acad. Pol. Des. Sci.*, 1975, **23**, 295.
18. G. H. CAREY and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2859.
19. A. E. MARTELL, S. CHABEREK, JR., S. C. COURTNEY, S. WESTERBACK and H. HYTIAMEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **79**, 3086.
20. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1968, **162**, 746 ; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.